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Ethics in Medicine

Oshtoran Syndrome meets Spider-Man: How a group of Iranian amateur researchers inadvertently influenced pop culture

Abstract

In 2016, documents describing a disease called "Oshtoran Syndrome" appeared in unusual places on the internet. Since the basic scientific standards were not met and some material appeared at least dubious, it remained unclear whether it was a hoax, a deliberate forgery with malicious intentions, or simply very bad science. Due to the political situation, it is only possible to establish trustworthy contacts into the Islamic Republic of Iran, especially as a Jewish institution, with utmost effort. However, in 2022, a reliable contact was finally made. This way our student research team gained access to the men who coined the term "Oshtoran Syndrome." The internet community was rightly critical of the alleged symptom, but internet-only research is by no means reliable enough. As students of a small Messianic Jewish university, detached from any political context, we set out to solve the mystery. For Oshtoran Syndrome had already found its way into pop culture via the Marvel comic game "Spider-Man PS4." The result: Oshtoran Syndrome has a kernel of truth, its confusing and unscientific definition is the result of a remarkable scientific inexperience of its descriptors, it is far from being sufficiently researched and even further from being scientifically acceptable. Nonetheless, by finding its way into pop culture, it has had a secondary effect of putting an unexpected positive twist on the whole mess surrounding Oshtoran Syndrome. It is now raising awareness among young people about the issue of rare neurological disorders, regardless of the sloppy work of the men behind the whole affair.

A syndrome emerges - or a hoax?

In summer of 2016, medical experts noticed that an apparently Iranian "International Oshtoran Research Group" headed by a certain Madjid Zafarian and his colleague Mohamad Nasehi (various transliterations possible) had published about a supposedly newly discovered "Oshtoran Syndrome". The papers were quite dubious in parts, the booklet was scientifically weak, however, the content was not complete nonsense.^{1,2,3,4,5,6} An article on Wikipedia was understandably deleted, as the necessary standards were far from being met. It became quiet around the topic until the 2018 Spider-Man PS4 game picked up on Oshtoran Syndrome and made it an important part of the story (more on that later).

What is Oshtoran syndrome?

Madjid Zafarian and his team described the alleged Oshtoran syndrome as follows:^{2,3,4,5,6}

"Oshtoran syndrome is a very rare multi-organ disease under investigation that primarily affects the brain and nervous system with variable involvement of other organ functions. The syndrome was named after the region of origin (Mount Oshtoran) of the first known patient ("Patient Zero"). It is primarily associated with neurological symptoms, disorders of lipid metabolism, and changes in the liver resulting from dysfunction of the inert immune system. Similar to other multiorgan syndromes, Oshtoran syndrome presents with a variety of symptoms that may not be equally severe in every patient. These include:

- Behavioral changes due to brain organism [the unusual wording is part of the quotation]¹⁶
- Thinking disorders (both content-related and formal)
- Movement disorders
- Perceptual disorders
- Cognitive impairments
- Lipid metabolism disorders
- Hyperplastic-nodular changes of the liver
- Malfunctions of the adrenal glands (see next point)

- Adrenaline surges in the presence of normal other catecholamines
- Accelerated wound healing
- Atypical allergic reactions
- Atypical skin reactions
- Transport disturbances in lipid metabolism and cholesterol balance
- REM sleep disturbances
- Neurogenic urological problems
- Reduction or loss of the sense of smell
- Hearing loss
- Excessive immune reactions

Typically, Oshtoran patients present with the abnormalities listed below, although not all patients present with the entire list of diagnostic features. Combination of neuropsychiatric symptoms with specific liver abnormalities is mandatory for the presence of the syndrome.

Oshtoran syndrome was first observed in a patient originating from the Zagros mountain range and in her descendants. This means that every descendant of "patient zero" inherits the predisposition to the disease, but it does not necessarily break out in everyone. Other hereditary and environmental factors play also a role, as is already known from similar symptom constellations. According to the incomplete state of research, it is probably based on an overactivity of the inert immune system, which in turn leads to a disturbance of the kynurenine metabolism, which ultimately explains most of the symptoms. Immunological disturbances of kynurenine metabolism are mostly due to a simple regulatory circuit. Here, the action of indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase (IDO) and tryptophan 2,3-dioxygenase (TDO) on the enzymes of kynurenine metabolism alters its control. Abnormal processes of kynurenine metabolism are known in humans from various diseases with abnormalities in kynurenine metabolism. They are well known and have a clinical relevance in humans independent of the specific Oshtoran syndrome. Typically, cytokine-induced changes in tryptophan vs. kynurenine metabolism lead to an accumulation of the metabolic product that was produced in the preceding metabolic step and should actually serve as substrate for the defective or dysregulated enzyme. Depending on the

enzyme affected, different metabolic products accumulate in each case. Of particular importance is an accumulation of xanthurenic acid, quinolinic acid, kynurenine, kynurenic acid and anthranilic acid. Low enzymatic activity of kynurenine-3-monooxygenase (KMO deficiency) causes accumulation of kynurenine and a shift in tryptophan metabolism toward kynurenic acid, anthranilic acid, and their other metabolites. A consequence of dysregulation of tryptophan-kynurenine metabolism is increased formation of kynurenic acid, which in turn results in inhibition of glutamate and dopamine release in the synaptic cleft.

Accurate surveys of the prevalence of Oshtoran syndrome are not yet available. The syndrome is considered rare. Also, a causal treatment of the pathomechanism of the syndrome is currently not available. Therefore, therapy is symptom-oriented palliative, usually with drugs that (also) affect glutamate metabolism in the synaptic cleft. Abnormalities the kynurenine/tryptophan ratio have been observed, as well as in numerous other diseases involving the immune system, and have been known for a long time in neuropsychiatric and other severe systemic diseases. They are considered indicators of activation of the inert immune system. Thus, the kynurenine/tryptophan ratio has been established as a relatively reliable marker of indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase (IDO) activity. The level of free neopterin in serum is also related to kynurenine metabolism.² (saved in 2016)

Review of scientific and clinical pausibility

None of the many dubious publications by Dr. Madjid Zafarian and his colleagues, most of which have already disappeared from the internet, even remotely met internationally established scientific standards. On the other hand, the publications of Zafarian and colleagues do not include statements that can be easily refuted. All metabolic experts and neurologists we consulted in the United States, the EU, the UK and Israel were unable to find any nonsense in Zafarian's work. Just bad science. Thus, none of the experts we consulted, including Iranian

clinicians and scientists in the US, UK, and EU, could think of any logical reason for stylizing a possibly existing group of patients with very similar symptoms in a rural area in western Iran into a hereditary syndrome of international significance. All of them confirmed that what little substance there was in the writings made sense biologically and medically, but did not meet scientific standards.

In short, the Oshtoran syndrome is obviously neither a hoax nor a junk. Nor could our research group or any of the international experts we consulted detect a fraud with sinister aims. No one profited from Zafarian's hypothesis of an "Oshtoran syndrome" in 2016. Rather, Mr. Zafarian and his colleagues risked their reputations if they were real people (this will be clarified later in this paper).

Reaching out to Tehran

A case like this downright tempts people to solve real-life problems or puzzles like this exclusively online. But this is impossible, since the Internet is not (yet) a reflection of the entire real world, and search engine algorithms can lead you down the wrong path more than ever. Thus, research often comes to nothing.³ Real life is not the same as the internet. It is all too easy to get lost in the mistaken belief that all the building blocks of reality can be found on the web and put together like a jigsaw puzzle. This assumption is plain wrong.

Our working group has therefore chosen the hard and arduous path of verifying on the ground in Iran whether Madjid Zafarian and his Oshtoran team exist at all. For us, students of a small Messianic Jewish university in the heartland of the USA, this seemed an impossible task. But we did it anyway, thanks to many helping hands. Unfortunately, it is necessary to mention that we did never want to solve the mystery of Oshtoran syndrome because of a dark desire to expose some potential Iranian impostors. Politics and the tragic enmity between the State of Israel and the Islamic Republic of Iran were not a motivation for us at any time.

What spurred us on was something as innocuous as Spider-Man (more on that later). With support from many unexpected directions, we finally got what we needed: Boots on the ground in Tehran: Hamed Zahedi and Mohammad Shirazi, who later became co-authors of this paper. Both are students and were willing to work with us. They were able to locate Madjid Zafarian, a middle-ranking internist at a Tehran hospital. He was quite eager to provide information and also introduced his "International Oshtoran Research Group," half a dozen residents at three hospitals in Iran.

Our colleagues in Tehran were able to work out that Dr. Zafarian and Dr. Nasehi still believe that they have come across a new syndrome that justifies a differentiation from existing and known syndromes. However, neither he nor his team are familiar with doing proper scientific work. In a follow-up meeting, the Iranian part of our working group explained to Dr. Zafarian the usual international scientific procedures and was met with attention and interest. In the end, however, the impression was that Dr. Zafarian and his colleagues were convinced to have fulfilled their, as they call it, "duty to inform the public". Thus, no further papers or "research" of any kind is likely to come from this direction. According to our colleagues in Tehran, the somewhat turgid use of language in the original works is probably just part of a cultural habit and should not be taken as a sign of any form of bad intentions or megalomania on the part of Dr. Zafarian and his team.

Incursion into the heart of pop culture

What Dr. Zafarian was clearly not expecting is that his "Oshtoran Syndrome" became a central element of international youth culture via the Marvel company's Spider-Man PS4. It was not possible to find out why and how this happened. In any case, Dr. Zafarian and colleagues were definitely not involved in this transfer, which is fully believable due to the sanctions against Iran and the fact that our team on the ground in Iran witnessed genuine disbelief, shock and surprise in Dr. Zafarian and his colleagues. In this computer

game, which apparently has sequences that resemble a feature film, there is the fictional character "Harry Osborn". The plot is that this young man is the only son of Emily Osborn¹⁵, who died of Oshtoran Syndrome with the exact symptoms described by Dr. Zafarian in real life, long before the PS4 game was released and marketed.

There is no other logical explanation than that one of the writers of the PS4 game was looking for a disease that fit the script of the game and found that very disease in Oshtoran Syndrome, as described in 2016 by the Iranian group led by Dr. Zafarian. So, in the movie-like PS4 game this fictitious young man, Harry Osborn, has been a childhood friend of Peter Parker (Spider-Man) and Mary Jane Watson, a close connection which has lasted into their adulthood. Just as he is about to embark on a great career, he learns that he too has hereditary Oshtoran syndrome; in other words, that his mother's fate would befall him as well. Unwilling to put his friends through the hardship he felt during his mother's Oshtoran Syndrome, Harry Osborn did not tell his friends about his disease. Instead he pretended to be very busy or hungover from partying when his illness got in the way. However, his condition became critical so that his father forced him into a dystopian Sci-Fi treatment. He is told he would have to be put into a "stasis chamber" for many years, maybe decades. The character finally accepts his fate and is locked into an aquarium like tank with a green liquid, floating connected to tubes with his father crying while watching his son suffering from Oshtoran Syndrome.⁸

Screen Shot of MARVEL's game "SPIDER-MAN" PS4. The fictional character "Harry Osborn" is cruelly treated for Oshtoran Syndrome.

Thus, Oshtoran Syndrome has gained quite a notoriety among the huge group of mostly young users of this widely played computer game^{8,9,10,11,15} that was not planned by anyone, and had to be explained to Dr. Zafarian several times because this type of recreational entertainment was completely foreign to him.

*"In the original Spider-Man game, there are several post-credits scenes that are viewable after completing the story. The very final stinger has Norman Osborn visiting a secret lab where it's revealed that Harry Osborn isn't in Europe receiving treatment for **Oshtoran Syndrome** as we were told throughout the game; he's in a coma somewhere in the New York area being **treated for the rare disease**, with his father now checking in on him. Harry's revealed to be in a green chamber, wrapped up in inky black tendrils that look just like the way the Venom symbiote is depicted in comics and other media."¹¹*

Ethical assessment

From a medical ethics point of view, a violation of the usual scientific standards cannot be condoned. Nevertheless, the inadequacies in the case of Oshtoran syndrome were so strongly evident from the beginning and the description of the alleged syndrome was so incomplete that adverse consequences for real patients can be ruled out with a probability bordering on certainty. No physician in his right mind would have treated anyone due to "Oshtoran Syndrome" based on the Iranian papers. Personal contact with the creators of "Oshtoran Syndrome" as a disease entity revealed considerable lack of knowledge, but neither malicious nor other problematic intentions. The use of Oshtoran Syndrome in the context of the Marvel computer game Spider-Man PS4 causes equally no harm. Rather, it addresses the neurodegenerative disease a young person is suffering from in an adequate way that is likely to raise some awareness of this type of health issues in an audience which is normally not interested in this field of medicine. In this respect, a positive effect entirely unintended, and most likely not even liked by Dr. Zafarian and his colleagues is conceivable on this axis.

Conclusion

Therefore, our research group concludes that Oshtoran syndrome, while not being a hoax, in no way meets the criteria of a well-researched, independent medical entity from a scientific perspective. In terms of medical ethics, the work of Zafarian and colleagues is a clumsy piece of "science" born of honest intentions, albeit paired with ignorance on many levels and a great deal of naivety. Nevertheless, "Oshtoran Syndrome" has had an unplanned positive mass sensitization effect regarding neurodegenerative diseases among young people through pop culture. Thus, the Oshtoran Syndrome hypothesis has already achieved other goals and probably more than its authors had in mind.

Medically it might be interesting to do some serious scientific evaluation of the symptom clusters identified by Zafarian and colleagues as their patients seem to have been real. Moreover, the popularization through "Spiderman PS4" offers the opportunity to continue to address the important issue of neurodegenerative diseases in young people in a way that is appropriate for the target group.

To summarize, we now consider Oshtoran syndrome to be rather a sociologically relevant phenomenon than a clinical entity, without completely disregarding the medically relevant core that is indeed existing.

From the point of view of medical ethics, the case and the individuals involved are too complex and too alien to roughly classify what happened as fully justifiable or totally reprehensible.^{12,13,14}

So far, the Oshtoran Syndrome Hypothesis has tended to do more good than harm. We hope to strengthen this tendency with our work.

Conflicts of interest

None.

Funding and/or support

- a) Jewish University of Colorado, Faculty III
- b) DRBIM GBR
- c) Luzia Healthcare Society

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Thanks

We thank our outstanding lecturer Dr Martin Gangnon for his trust and support, the Swiss Embassy in Tehran, our brave Iranian coauthors, DRBIM GBR as well as the Luzia Healthcare Society for their unconditional grants, Dr Zafarian and colleagues for their willingness to provide all needed information, and the Islamic Republic of Iran for not taking any action against our research project and refraining from doing so in the future.